

Data management plan: Enhanced Security and Energy Efficiency Hybrid Chaotic Communication System (Nr. RTU-PA-2024/1-0064)

Version 1

Description

Development grant No RTU-PA-2024/1-0064. under the EU RRF project No 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/003.

The project aims to create new knowledge and technological insights by researching hybrid solutions for high-security, energy-efficient chaotic communication systems. Its novelty lies in integrating sensor nodes with analog chaotic generators and a universal gateway, including the generator's digital implementation in a single embedded system, and ensuring hybrid chaotic synchronization of these components. Research activities include analyzing the nonlinear dynamics of chaotic generators using the Method of Complete Bifurcation Groups developed by RTU, applying the offset-boosting methodology for generating security keys, eliminating reverse-engineering, enhancing energy efficiency, and reducing synchronization time. The project will integrate analog and digital implementations of chaotic generators into a secure communication system, model the system, and conduct practical and experimental research. The expected outcome is a methodology for a new type of chaotic communication system based on the hybrid synchronization of analog and digital chaos generators and an additional layer of physical security. The project plans to publish three scientific articles (at least two Q1/Q2 articles co-authored with a QS WUR TOP500 researcher), prepare teaching materials, attract two researchers for thesis development, and prepare an international project application.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

Data management plan:
Enhanced Security and Energy
Efficiency Hybrid Chaotic
Communication System (Nr.
RTU-PA-2024/1-0064)

Researchers

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Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Data management plan: Enhanced Security and Energy Efficiency Hybrid Chaotic Communication System (Nr. RTU-PA-2024/1-0064)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: [Data management plan: Enhanced Security and Energy Efficiency Hybrid Chaotic Communication System \(Nr. RTU-PA-2024/1-0064\)](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2025-03-31](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Chaotic oscillators simulation results

The project will generate simulation results from chaotic oscillator circuits simulated in LTspice. The data will consist of waveform plots (voltage, current, phase-space diagrams) captured during parameter variation studies. All results will be compiled and provided in PDF format. Optional supporting files (e.g., schematic screenshots or tables) may also be embedded in the PDFs.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The simulation results illustrate new dynamic behaviors in chaotic oscillators when certain component values or system parameters are changed. These results support research into chaos-based electronics, secure communications, and nonlinear system modelling. Obtained in LTSpice simulation environment.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No, all data will be original and produced as part of this project.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers in nonlinear dynamics, electronics design, chaos theory, and graduate-level students exploring simulation of chaotic systems.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

IEEE keywords

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

LTSpice, pdf tools.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

The primary format for sharing simulation results will be PDF, which is a widely used open standard (ISO 32000) and readable on all platforms. However, PDF is not ideal for automated data extraction or recombination with other datasets.

To address this, key data points (e.g., parameter values, measured quantities, bifurcation points) will also be included in open, machine-readable formats, such as:

CSV (.csv) for tabular results or parameter sweeps

TXT (.txt) for annotated notes or metadata

LTspice schematic files (.asc) if appropriate for reproducing the simulations

This combination ensures that the dataset remains human-readable, but also supports basic levels of interoperability and reuse in data analysis tools and software pipelines.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.3.3 Other relevant remarks

Given the nature of the dataset — simulation results from LTspice in PDF format — the use of formal data vocabularies or taxonomies is not considered necessary. The data is intended primarily for human interpretation (e.g., visualization of dynamic behavior) rather than machine-based integration or automated analysis.

However, clear and consistent naming, basic metadata (e.g., file titles, simulation parameters), and accompanying documentation will be provided to ensure usability and understanding by other researchers in the field.

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-05-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2026-05-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Data quality is ensured through several internal verification steps:

All simulations will be run multiple times in LTspice to confirm reproducibility and consistency.

Parameter values, circuit topologies, and simulation settings will be carefully logged and cross-checked.

Each PDF file will be reviewed for clarity, correct labeling (e.g., axes, units), and completeness of results.

Supporting CSV or TXT files will be validated to ensure they match the plots and reflect the correct data ranges.

A final manual review will be conducted before publication to ensure that each file is self-contained and correctly documented.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Dmitrijs Pikulins (0000-0002-6768-6989)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Simulation results for the hybrid chaotic communication system

The dataset contains simulation results related to the development and analysis of a novel hybrid chaotic communication system (HCCS). This system integrates analogue chaotic oscillators used in low-power sensor nodes with digitally implemented chaotic oscillators (FPGA-based) used in a universal gateway. Simulations include chaotic signal generation, hybrid synchronization techniques (analogue-to-digital and digital-to-analogue), and implementation of Quadrature Chaos Shift Keying (QCSK)

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The primary purpose of collecting and generating this dataset is to validate and optimize the performance of a novel hybrid chaotic communication system (HCCS). The data supports the evaluation of chaotic synchronization mechanisms, offset-boosting security techniques, Quadrature Chaos Shift Keying (QCSK) modulation efficiency, and overall energy efficiency. These simulations directly relate to the project's key objectives—ensuring robust synchronization, enhancing communication security, achieving optimal power consumption, and confirming scalability for real-world IoT applications.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

300

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The current project focuses on developing a novel hybrid chaotic communication system employing previously unexplored synchronization methods and innovative offset-boosting techniques. While the underlying theoretical concepts and general chaotic system models described in existing scientific literature serve as foundational references, no pre-existing datasets meet the specific research requirements or include the novel synchronization scenarios and modulation schemes proposed by this project. Therefore, the reuse of existing datasets is not feasible, and new simulation data generation is necessary to fulfill the project's unique objectives.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The simulation data generated by the project could be useful to several stakeholder groups:

- Scientific community. Researchers focusing on nonlinear dynamics, chaotic systems, secure wireless communications, and synchronization techniques.
- Industry professionals. Engineers and developers working on IoT systems, wireless sensor networks, cybersecurity solutions, and energy-efficient communication technologies.

- Academic institutions and educators. University lecturers and students involved in teaching or learning courses related to signal processing, embedded systems, and nonlinear electronics.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Dublin Core

Yes. Comprehensive metadata will be provided alongside the datasets. Metadata will include detailed descriptions of the dataset content, context, methodologies, simulation parameters, software and hardware specifications, dates of data generation, and project references. This metadata will adhere to widely-recognized standards (e.g., Dublin Core) to ensure enhanced discoverability, accessibility, and usability in accordance with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The generated datasets will be accessible using common, open-source, or widely-used software tools, ensuring broad accessibility and usability. The primary software tools and methods include: **Numerical Simulation Data (.csv, .txt files)**

- Spreadsheet software: MS Excel, LibreOffice Calc, Google Sheets
- Programming languages: Python (with pandas or NumPy libraries), MATLAB/Octave, R.

Simulation Scripts and Source Code (.m, .py, .vhd, .v files)

- MATLAB scripts: MATLAB or GNU Octave for script execution.
- Python scripts: Python environment (Python 3.x) and standard libraries.
- FPGA source files: FPGA development tools such as Xilinx Vivado, Intel Quartus Prime, or open-source tools like GHDL for VHDL files.

Visual and Graphical Data (.png, .svg files)

- Raster images: Standard image viewers available on any operating system.
- Vector graphics: Web browsers, vector graphics editors (e.g., Inkscape, Adobe Illustrator).

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

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2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-12-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2026-12-31

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Dmitrijs Pikulins (0000-0002-6768-6989)

The Scientific Leader and Senior Researcher will oversee the overall data management strategy, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles. Researchers and PhD students involved in each work package (WP1-WP4) will be responsible for generating, documenting, and organizing datasets within their specific tasks. Regular data backups, metadata preparation, and quality checks will be conducted throughout the project's duration.

Finalized datasets and associated metadata will be deposited in selected open repositories by designated team members, ensuring proper documentation, accessibility, and long-term preservation. The Scientific Leader will coordinate and supervise the entire data management process, facilitating consistency, accuracy, and timely publishing of data.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

The project datasets intended for public sharing will not contain sensitive or confidential information and thus will be openly accessible to the general public.

However, during the active research phase and prior to public release, the following data security measures will be implemented:

Password Protection

During data generation, processing, and internal storage, access to datasets and associated tools will be secured with strong, unique passwords. Password management tools (e.g., Bitwarden, KeePass) will be used to maintain secure access control.

Controlled Access (Pre-publication phase)

Before publicly released data, access will be limited to authorized project team members only.

Secure Storage and Encryption (Internal Use):

Before public distribution, data will be securely stored using institutional infrastructure (RTU-secured servers and cloud platforms) with appropriate encryption standards (e.g., AES-256) to prevent unauthorized access or data leakage.

After public release, datasets will be deposited into trusted repositories, eliminating the need for further password protection and allowing unrestricted public access according to FAIR data principles.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

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